

EFFECTS OF ISOTHERMAL AGING ON THE TOUGHNESS OF POLYMERIC COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Mode I and mode II fracture toughness tests were performed on unidirectional Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) and End Notch Flexure (ENF) specimens, respectively, after elevated temperature aging. Aging temperatures of 150°C, 177°C, and 204°C with aging times up to 9 months (6480 hr) were used. Graphite/thermoplastic and graphite/bismaleimide material systems were studied. Thermoplastic fracture toughness decreased at higher temperatures, while thermoset (bismaleimide) fracture toughness remained equal to or greater than room temperature values. Fracture toughness for both materials was found to decrease with aging initially, and then increase after long aging times.

BACKGROUND

The high performance characteristics of composites, along with the improved technologies in propulsion, make possible the development of an economically viable passenger aircraft capable of supersonic cruise. At a cruise speed of Mach 2.4, the structural components of the airplane will be subjected to an elevated temperature environment. Therefore, it is necessary to determine the effect of long duration exposure to high temperature on the performance of composite structural components. One important design criterion for using composite materials in primary structure is delamination onset and growth in laminates. This study focused on characterizing the elevated temperature aging effects on fracture toughness of composite laminates.

The aging effects were primarily studied using mechanical testing. Chemical testing of the material system is needed to properly determine the causes of the results reported in this paper. We know that thermal aging causes molecular degradation through chain scission, loss of side groups, loss of volatiles, and oxidation [1-3]. Physical aging is also an important parameter in polymeric material aging [4]. The effects of these molecular changes will be discussed in this paper. However, these changes should be verified with experimental data.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The research program began in 1991, with testing of graphite/bismaleimide IM7/5260. Shorter aging times were planned for study at higher temperatures, due to increased degradation rates. However, after testing mode I specimens aged at 177°C and 204°C, it was determined that degradation rates did not vary enough to warrant the different aging times. The resulting test matrix is shown in Tables 1 and 2. A second research program was begun in 1993, to perform similar experiments on a graphite/polyimide, IM7/K3B. This research is currently in progress, with testing completed for aging times up to 9 months (6480 hr). The complete test matrix is shown in Table 3, with completed tests shown in bold letters. Note that some specimens for shorter aging times have been added to the test matrix only recently, and have not yet been tested.

Table 1. Test matrix for IM7/5260

Aging/Test Temperature	Fracture Mode	Aging Time (months)				
		0	1	3	6	12
22°C/22°C	Mode I	5	-	-	-	-
22°C/22°C	Mode II	3	-	-	-	-
150°C/150°C	Mode I	5	5	5	5	-
150°C/150°C	Mode II	3	3	3	3	3
177°C/177°C	Mode I	5	5	5	5	-
177°C/177°C	Mode II	5	3	3	3	-
204°C/204°C	Mode II	5	4	4	4	-

Table 2. Test matrix for IM7/5260, 204°C mode I testing

Aging/Test Temperature	Fracture Mode	Aging Time (months)				
		0	0.3	0.8	1.4	1.9
204°C/204°C	Mode I	5	5	5	5	5

Table 3. Test matrix for IM7/K3B

Aging/Test Temperature	Fracture Mode	Aging Time (months)							
		0	1	3	6	9	12	15	18
177°C/22°C	Mode I	5	-	5	-	5	-	-	-
177°C/22°C	Mode II	5	-	5	-	5	-	-	-
150°C/150°C	Mode I	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
150°C/150°C	Mode II	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
177°C/177°C	Mode I	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
177°C/177°C	Mode II	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
204°C/204°C	Mode I	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	-
204°C/204°C	Mode II	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	-

END NOTCH FLEXURE TEST

Laminate curing was performed by the material supplier. Panels had a unidirectional (10/D/10) layup, where D denotes a delamination insert. These panels were cut into specimen dimensions at the University of Washington using a fluid cooled diamond cutting wheel. Specimens were 15.25 cm by 2.54 cm, with the long axis in the fiber direction. Specimens had an average thickness of 0.282 cm. Specimens were pre-cracked in mode I before aging to move the exposed crack tip beyond the resin rich region at the edge of the delamination insert.

The specimens were isothermally aged in three air circulating ovens. Specimens were removed from the oven and weighed once each month. No weight changes were found for K3B specimens at the resolution of the scale used, ±0.01 g. Weight data for 5260 specimens was not recorded.

The prepared specimen was inserted into an aluminum test fixture, designed to hold the specimen in a three point bend with the crack tip midway between the center load and one end. This fixture was placed in an air circulating testing oven. Loading was supplied by a variable speed displacement controlled load arm at 0.25 cm/min, and measured by a load cell. Displacement was

Fig. 1. Typical loading curve for mode II fracture toughness testing

measured by a clip gage located on the loading arm, outside the oven. Corrections were made in displacement measurement to account for extension of the load line. Voltage measurements were recorded by a personal computer through a data acquisition board. Data acquisition rate was approximately 2 readings per second.

G_{IIc} values were calculated using beam theory with corrections for transverse shear [5] as given in Eqn (1). P_c and δ_c are the load and displacement at the critical point, a is the crack length, b the specimen width, L the half length, and h the half thickness of the beam.

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{9P_c \delta_c a^2}{2b(2L^3 + 3a^2)} \left[1 + 0.2 \left(\frac{E_{II}}{G_{I3}} \right) \left(\frac{h}{a} \right)^2 \right] \quad (1)$$

The critical point was determined as the nonlinear point in the load vs. displacement curve, as shown in the example of Fig. 1. The plot shown is for a specimen being tested at 204°C. Note that specimens at elevated temperature showed a plastic crack growth zone, whereas specimens at room temperature had a sudden drop in displacement at the critical point. Half span and crack length were measured directly from the specimen after completion of the test.

DOUBLE CANTILEVER BEAM TEST

Mode I DCB specimens were fabricated, cut, and aged as for ENF testing, except that the specimen length was 23.00 cm. End blocks were bonded to the specimens for load application using a high temperature adhesive system. The curing process for this adhesive was considered insignificant compared with the aging times of the study. After end blocks were in place, the edge of the specimens were painted white and increments marked at 0.25 in. intervals with a razor blade to aid in locating the crack tip during testing. Loading pins were inserted into the end blocks, to provide a mode I opening of the crack tip. The testing oven, load application and measuring devices were the same as described for mode II testing.

Fracture toughness was quantified by calculating G_{Ic} using the area method. This method equates the area under the curve of one loading and unloading cycle, highlighted in the example shown in Fig. 2, to the energy absorbed during crack growth. By measuring crack length before and after the loading cycle, crack extension is determined. G_{Ic} is the energy absorbed per unit length of crack growth. Other methods for calculating G_{Ic} using critical values of load and displacement, along with beam theory equations, are found in the literature [5, 6]. G_{Ic} calculations using these methods are being conducted, but were unavailable at the time of publication.

Fig. 2. Typical loading curves for mode I fracture toughness testing

The maximum load for loading curves near the crack tip are smaller than those in the interior of the specimen. This shape was typical of all specimens tested at elevated temperature, while room temperature tests had peak load values near the crack tip. Results reported in this paper are averaged from loading curves away from the crack tip, so do not include this effect. The phenomena will be studied further and reported in future papers.

RESULTS

MODE II FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

Mode II fracture toughness depended on testing temperature for both material systems. Fig. 3 shows the results of all specimens tested with zero aging. K3B is superior to 5260 at all temperatures tested. The variation in fracture toughness comes from two opposing influences. Approaching the glass transition temperature (T_g) of a material will reduce the fracture toughness, as can be seen in the thermoplastic K3B. The materials tested had a T_g of approximately 216°C . At 204°C , the material is close to the transition region of the material. In cross-linked materials, such as the 5260, the increased bond energy gained from higher temperatures will drive stiffness up. This effect offsets the influence of approaching T_g and the net result is an equivalent fracture toughness for tests conducted at room temperature, 177°C , and 204°C .

Fig. 4 shows G_{IIc} values for aged specimens. The main difference between the two material systems in terms of fracture toughness is the overall starting superiority of K3B. For the aging times studied, aged K3B specimens maintain higher fracture toughness values. Another difference between the two systems is a post-cure effect that K3B undergoes, which is not seen in 5260. The post-cure effect is primarily dependent on the curing cycle. Changing the curing procedure could greatly alter the initial response, but would not greatly influence the long term aging characteristics of the material.

While the scatter for the fracture toughness values shown is fairly large, the general trends for both systems are significant and consistent. For relatively short aging times, the fracture toughness of the aged material decreases. This effect is caused by chemical degradation in the polymer molecules.

After longer aging times, the downward trend in fracture toughness slows and eventually reverses. While it is likely that the degradation reactions eventually slow down and asymptotically approach zero as chemical reactions are carried to their fullest extent, the upturn in the fracture toughness is

Fig. 3. Mode II fracture toughness of specimens with zero aging

Fig. 4. Mode II fracture toughness of aged specimens

unlikely to be caused by these same reactions. Other possible sources of increasing fracture toughness were investigated, and the most probable cause was the increasing flexural stiffness of the specimens. This investigation is detailed in the section below.

FLEXURAL STIFFNESS

Flexural stiffness of a unidirectional ENF specimen is calculated using beam theory with a correction term for transverse shear [7] from the equation

$$E_{If} = \frac{2L^3 + 3a^3}{8Cwh^3} \left[1 + \frac{2(1.2L + 0.9a)h^2E_1}{(2L^3 + 3a^3)G_{13}} \right] \quad (2)$$

Compliance C is determined from a linear regression curve fit of the loading portion of the test curve, as in the example shown in Fig. 1. All other values were measured directly from the specimen, as explained previously.

Fig. 5. Flexural elastic modulus for aged ENF specimens

This increase in flexural stiffness results in higher loads for a given strain field, and thus increases fracture toughness at long aging times. At short aging times, this trend will also have the effect of driving fracture toughness values higher. However, polymer degradation dominates the changes at short aging times and the overall effect is decreasing fracture toughness.

The increase in flexural stiffness is explained by physical aging of the material. Physical aging causes an increase in density of the matrix without changing other properties, thereby increasing matrix stiffness. Note that the source of the increase in stiffness has not been verified, and should be investigated in a more thorough manner in future studies.

MODE I FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

Trends found for mode I fracture toughness were very similar to those for mode II fracture toughness. Values shown are for the area method, usually taking the average of loading curves away from the crack tip. As mentioned earlier, specimens tested at elevated temperature had lower fracture toughness values near the exposed crack tip. This phenomena has not been investigated fully, so a report on this topic is not included. Flexural modulus will be investigated for these specimens using the procedure given in [6] and reported in future publications.

Fig. 6. Mode I fracture toughness of specimens with zero aging

Fig. 7. Mode I fracture toughness of aged specimens

The K3B G_{Ic} fracture toughness values follow trends similar to mode II fracture toughness when plotted versus temperature for specimens with zero aging. As the material approaches the glass transition temperature, the material loses cohesiveness and fracture toughness decreases.

However, the mode I fracture toughness of 5260 specimens increases with temperature. For these specimens, the deformation is more severe than the mode II ENF specimens. The gains associated with increasing stiffness due to rising bond energy dominate, and fracture toughness increases.

As aging progresses, the changes in G_{IC} are almost identical to the changes in G_{IIc} . K3B has a sharp post-cure effect, while 5260 does not. For both material systems, there is an initial downward trend in the values, associated with polymer degradation. After longer aging times, the decrease slows, and then G_{IC} begins to increase. The explanation for these trends is that degradation reactions approach an equilibrium value, while flexural stiffness constantly increases due to physical aging. The net result is increasing fracture toughness at longer aging times.

SUMMARY

The effect of elevated temperature isothermal aging on the fracture toughness of two polymeric composite materials has been investigated. For the thermoplastic system studied, IM7/K3B, increasing temperature causes a decrease in fracture toughness. When tested at elevated temperatures, the thermoset IM7/5260 maintained fracture toughness values equal to or above room temperature values. However, even at the highest temperatures studied, the K3B fracture toughness properties were superior to those of 5260.

For both material systems studied, the fracture toughness of aged specimens generally decreases for a relatively short time period. At longer aging times fracture toughness levels off and begins to increase. The cause of short term decrease is believed to be chemical degradation of the polymer matrix. The long term increase is caused by increasing stiffness of the matrix, as shown by calculating flexural stiffness of the ENF specimens. These results will be very useful in predicting the durability of polymeric composites used in structures exposed to elevated temperatures.

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